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Research Paper

Knowledge System in Development of Energy Technology

ismita Singh

Manav Rachna International University

Abstract

The purpose of Energy study is to share that all life on earth depends upon energy. Energy from sun is used by plants to make food. Plant food is needed to sustain life by providing nourishment for our bodies and muscles. The sun's energy is also stored in coal, wood and oil, used to produce food and modify matter. All of the achievements of mankind were sustained through the use of energy. This is the time when human started utilizing fossil fuel to create cities that dwarf the ancient wonders and operate machines that do the

work of hundreds of humans in a fraction of the time. My study will show that how Development in Energy Technologies based on earth fossil fuels allow an exponential increase in the populations and the standards of living in industrializing states. This economic realignment had multiple effects, many of are still with us today: environmental degradation as greenhouse effect, global warming, and limited fossil fuel left.

My aim is to analyze knowledge system in Development of Energy Technologies from First Industrial Revolution till today. To understand Development of Energy Technologies, the events that occurred in past and continued till today are studied. Linkage between Research & development in energy technologies,

energy generation through fossils and natural resources as well as their impact on environment and contribution to society is explored. Policies and Legislations developed in order to obtain green clean

environment, to protect our natural resources and to manage equal distribution of resources and to avoid electricity black outs and brown outs.

Author Biography

ismita Singh, Manav Rachna International University

HOD, B.Sc., ID,

Faculty of Planning & Architecture,

MRIU, Faridabad

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